

**FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQARISH
INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI
NOMLI III ILMYI ONLAYN KONFERENSIYA**

**EMOTIONAL MEANS OF LANGUAGE AS A METHOD OF VERBAL
EXPRESSION OF A CRITICAL ATTITUDE TO REALITY**

Asia International university

Mukhammadiyeva Nigina Maxmudovna

Ismatova Halimabonu

History and philology department

Abstract: The article examines the emotional means of language in the function of oral expression of the critical attitude of the author of English essay texts to the transmitted message. Based on the work of local and foreign linguists, the author of the article determines the categorical status of emotion and connects the concept of "emotion" with the corresponding category of "expressiveness". Systematization of language tools aimed at verbal expression of feelings is carried out based on the tasks achieved through their use.

Key words: emotion; expressiveness; functions of language; verbal expression of feelings; essay; journalistic style.

The theory of speech genre originated from ancient times and remains one of the main issues of pragmatism. As relatively stable types of speech, genres are distinguished by a variety of forms that are a unique linguistic reflection of human activity. During the development of mass media, the concept of genre became an object of more detailed study, and there was an opportunity to talk about inter-style genres. In this regard, the problem of defining the main features of the genre as a whole, as well as individual genres, seems to be the most urgent.

In this article, it is planned to show what language tools can be used to verbally convey a critical attitude to the message. In order to determine the categorical status of emotionality, an analytical review of the literature on this topic is carried out, an attempt is made to connect emotionality with the corresponding category of expressiveness.

The genetic and functional dependence of communication on human activity was established within the framework of the activity paradigm that came from psychology to linguistics. Studying the text as a product of speech activity is

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inextricably linked with the concept of communicative situation, personality factor and solving communicative problems. In the process of communication, any text acts as a unity of meaningful-semantic and pragmatic principles, which is both a product and a result of communication.

In the text as an object of research, from the point of view of the activity approach, two aspects are distinguished, which are inextricably linked with each other: a set of linguistic tools. This installation is based on the position of W. Humboldt, who stated that the text is impossible without the recipient, because it is not a direct transmitter of content, but only in the form of images and emotional experiences. is the trigger of the corresponding mental phenomena. Thus, the expressive plan is one of the most important plans of the text: due to the communicative nature of the text, it serves as one of the means of implementing its pragmatic tasks. Expressiveness is traditionally understood as "an unusual and expressive thing associated with the neutrality of speech, the amplification of the signal transmitted to it through language expression, and its separation from the general flow." The founder of modern concepts of expressiveness Sh. Balli is considered. Studying syntactic means as a means of indirect expressiveness (as opposed to direct lexical means), he emphasized their ability to give an effective charge to speech. Sh.Bally also defined the concept of emotional coloring of the facts that make up the expressive system of the language, raised the issue of learning the language as a means of influence. In this way, to affect the listener and evoke a certain emotional response - this is the purpose of the emotional load.

Later, the concept of expressiveness became the object of research of local and foreign scientists. By the 80s of the 20th century, the main approaches to the study of the phenomenon of expressiveness were formed in Russian linguistics: semasiological (among its representatives are A. A. Ufimtseva, V. G. Gak, V. N. Teliya, V. I. Shakhovskiy) and linguostylistic (G. V. Stepanov, K. A. Dolinin, T. G. Vinokur, Y. N. Karaulov). , Developed by I. R. Galperin.

Within the framework of the first approach, words, phrases and syntactic structures in the language are studied as a system as units capable of expressing expressiveness. Special attention is paid to the study of expressive color vocabulary: the place of the expressive component in the meaning of lexical language units, the nominative mechanisms of forming a certain meaning, as well as the interrelationship of various components of word semantics are

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determined. Thus, within this approach, expressiveness is interpreted as a linguistic category and functions as a semantic marker of a word.

Proponents of the linguostylistic approach consider expressiveness at the level of speech, study ways of giving speech its originality and expressiveness. The main thing is the choice of means of successfully conveying the intentions of the speaker. Expressiveness is studied as a functional category that manifests itself in a communicative act and increases the expressive possibilities of speech. We cannot draw a clear line between the study of expressiveness in language and speech: expressiveness is expressed through the medium of language, but has a linguistic character that is manifested in speech. The expressiveness of speech is wider than the expressiveness of language, because it manifests itself as a result of the use of language tools. The expressiveness of the language is in the first place, because it determines the expressiveness of the speech, which is consciously formed by the author with the help of expressive means of expressiveness and stylistic methods.

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